

A Federated Multigraph Integration Approach for Connectional Brain Template Learning

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Abstract. The connectional brain template (CBT) is a compact representation (i.e., a single connectivity matrix) *multi-view brain networks* of a given population. CBTs are especially very powerful tools in brain dysconnectivity diagnosis as well as holistic brain mapping if they are learned properly –i.e., occupy the center of the given population. Even though accessing large-scale datasets is much easier nowadays, it is still challenging to upload all these clinical datasets in a server altogether due to the data privacy and sensitivity. Federated learning, on the other hand, has opened a new era for machine learning algorithms where different computers are trained together via a distributed system. Each computer (i.e., a client) connected to a server, trains a model with its local dataset and sends its learnt model weights back to the server. Then, the server aggregates these weights thereby outputting global model weights encapsulating information drawn from different datasets in a *privacy-preserving* manner. Such a pipeline endows the global model with a generalizability power as it implicitly benefits from the diversity of the local datasets. In this work, we propose *the first federated connectional brain template learning* (Fed-CBT) framework to learn how to integrate multi-view brain connectomic datasets collected by different hospitals into a single representative connectivity map. First, we choose a random fraction of hospitals to train our global model. Next, all hospitals send their model weights to the server to aggregate them. We also introduce a weighting method for aggregating model weights to take full benefit from all hospitals. Our model to the best of our knowledge is the first and only federated pipeline to estimate connectional brain templates using graph neural networks. Our Fed-CBT code is available at <https://github.com/basiralab/Fed-CBT>.

Keywords: connectional brain templates · federated learning · multigraph integration · graph neural networks · brain connectivity

1 Introduction

Technological advances and publicly open datasets in network neuroscience have made it possible to understand the function and structure of the human brain

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[1,2]. Such advances and datasets, in particular, help us better differentiate a population of healthy from unhealthy subjects by mapping and comparing their brain connectivities. Connectional brain templates, CBTs, are great templates of multimodal brain networks in terms of how they integrate complementary information from multi-view or multi-modal connectivity datasets for a given population [3,4,5]. A CBT can be a powerful representation of a population of multi-view brain connectomes if it is well-centered (i.e., achieves the minimum distance to all connectomes in the population) and discriminative (i.e., discriminates between brain states such as healthy and disordered) [5]. Nevertheless there are various barriers to estimating such a representative and holistic CBT from connectomic datasets collected from different sources (e.g., hospitals or clinical facilities).

Given a population of subjects, estimating a CBT is a challenging task due to the complexity, heterogeneity and high-dimensionality of multi-view connectomic datasets [5] as well as the inter-individual variability across subjects and brain views (e.g., structural and functional connectivities) [4]. To estimate such a brain template, [3] proposed clustering-based multi-view network fusion. [3] fuses different views of every subject into one view and then clusters these views based on the similarity of their connectivity patterns. Finally, it averages those views and generates a CBT of the population. Despite its good results, its performance heavily depends on the number of clusters used during the fusion step. To eliminate this problem, [4] offered netNorm framework, which forms a tensor containing common cross-view features across subjects and then fuses distinct layers of this tensor into a CBT of the given population in a non-linear manner. In spite of its promising results, [4] has various limitations. First, it uses Euclidean distance as a dissimilarity metric to choose the most representative connections; however, this prevents the framework from capturing non-linear patterns. Second, netNorm consists of independent components which inhibits the training of the proposed framework in an end-to-end fashion. Another attempt for estimating CBT is [5]. Deep Graph Normalizer, DGN for short, presents the first graph neural network (GNN) to learn a CBT from a given multigraph population. DGN also introduces a novel loss, SNL, that optimizes the model to create a CBT that is well-centered and representative. However, SNL loss function does not evaluate how topological soundness of generated CBT is [6]. To alleviate this, [6] designed MGN-Net framework, which involves a novel loss function that forces the model to learn a topologically sound CBT while preserving the population distinctive traits.

However, all these methods share a prime challenge. To produce a highly representative CBT of a particular brain state, one needs to cover all the normative variations of that state –which is only possible when collecting from different global sources (e.g., hospitals or clinical facilities). However, clinical data sharing is a sensitive research topic with diverse ethical ramifications with regard to data privacy and protection protocols. Federated learning, on the other hand, is an emerging field with lots of promises such as data privacy, decentralized training, data variability and so on [7]. It is mainly rooted in the concept of

training local models, called clients, with their own datasets and sending their updated weights to a server. This server then aggregates those weights in order to have global weights gathered from clients without really using their local private datasets.

Federated learning has various medical applications. [8] offered a federated named entity recognition (NER) pipeline since data diversity is significant yet hard to gather in NER due to privacy issues. In this way, the global model in the pipeline can boost the training. [9] proposed an algorithm to detect COVID-19 while leveraging datasets in their own medical institutions using federated learning. They designed a dynamic fusion-based federated approach in order to alleviate the cost of transferring model updates and data heterogeneity of default setting of federated learning. [10] presented a federated pipeline to take advantage of big data for better understanding brain disorders. [11] introduced a medical relation extraction model to detect and classify semantic relationships from biomedical text using federated learning. Their method also includes knowledge distillation in order to defuse communication bottleneck. [12] suggested a federated learning approach to solve the problem of multi-site functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) classification combined with two domain adaptation methods. [13] offered a new federated learning approach other than [14] which is a channel-based update algorithm, more suitable for medical data – among others. **Although promising, none of these methods addressed the problem of connectomic data integration across a pool of hospitals [15].** To fill this gap, we propose a federated multigraph integration framework, namely Fed-CBT, in which different hospitals estimate their CBTs based on their local datasets and share their model weights with a server so that the server aggregates them in a way that the global model can benefit from all hospitals’ datasets. **This work is a primer, proposing the first federated GNN-based framework for multi-view graph fusion.**

2 Proposed Method

In this section, we give details about the components of the proposed method. Fed-CBT strategy consists of two main components: A) Training c fraction of hospitals and sending the models’ weights to the server and B) Averaging the models’ weights with designated strategy and updating hospitals in a federated manner. First, a DGN model [5] is initialized in the server and its weights are shared with hospitals that will be actively trained in the current round. Hospitals that are not trained in the current round do not update their weights. Thus, they just pass back their weights to the server. Other hospitals, however, are trained with their own datasets. We noticed that updating some fraction of hospitals accelerates the global model convergence. In each round, each hospital (client) randomly samples a subset from its local dataset for training and passes only one brain multigraph (i.e., subject connectivity tensor) to the DGN model composed of 3 layers of edge-conditioned convolution [16] in every batch. Several tensor operations (**Fig. 1**) are applied to the output feature vector and a CBT that

Fig. 1: Federated connectional brain template (Fed-CBT) learning framework for integrating multi-view brain networks collected from different hospitals. Here we illustrate one round of federated learning pipeline. Purple hospitals represent the hospitals trained during this round whereas blue ones represent those left-out. Arrow with point-like dash (a) implies that deep-copied weights of all layers are sent from hospitals to the server for averaging. Dashed arrow (b) implies that averaged weights of all layers are sent to all hospitals. Arrow (c), finally, implies the input-output flow between different operations. We give explanation of phase A and B next. **(A) Training c fraction of hospitals and sending models' weights to the server.** In each round, hospitals are randomly selected to be trained using their datasets. Features obtained from the last layer of DGN models are used to a generate CBT. After training, these hospitals send their updated model weights to the server while rest of the hospitals send what they receive. **(B) Global model update strategy.** Following the collection of the models' weights in the server, their weights are averaged with temporary-weighted averaging [17] in a layer-wise manner. Thus an updated version of the global model is generated. Next, weights of the updated global model are sent to hospitals trained in the current round.

represents the population of the dataset of a hospital is then generated. The learned CBT is evaluated against a randomly sampled subset of the local training dataset of the hospital using the loss function (**Eq. 2**) in order to optimize the model in a way that it generates a more centered CBT of the training dataset.

In order to have a compact implementation of the proposed algorithm, we keep weight transfer between all hospitals and the server in every round. This means, for all non-trained hospitals in a round, all they need to do is just send back weights coming from the server. We also state above that trained hospitals send their updated weights to the server. The server receives the weights of all DGN layers from all hospitals and averages them in a layer-wise manner using temporary-weighted averaging strategy [17]. In this way, the more lately a model is trained, the more its weights contribute to the global model. This weighted strategy prevents the global model from losing recently trained models weights by averaging without taking how lately a hospital gets involved in the federation training round. Following the update of the weights of the global model, these weights are sent to all hospitals with a new list of hospitals that will be trained in the following round. We detail this cross-hospital data integration pipeline in what follows. We have also presented significant mathematical notations used in this paper in **Table. 1**.

Table 1: *Significant mathematical notations used in the paper.* We denote tensors and matrices by Euler script letters (i.e. \mathcal{T}) and bold uppercase letters (i.e. \mathbf{M}), respectively. Vectors and scalars, on the other hand, are denoted by bold lowercase letters (i.e. \mathbf{v}) and italic lowercase letters (i.e. s). We use italic uppercase letters for sets (i.e. \mathcal{TH}).

Notation	Definition
c	fraction of hospitals trained in each round
e	number of local epochs in each round
n	number of hospitals
\mathcal{TH}^t	set of hospitals trained in round t
H^t	set of untrained hospitals in round t
\mathcal{T}_j	training set of multi-view brain networks of hospital j
n_v	number of brain networks of a subject
n_r	number of nodes (anatomical regions) in a brain network
\mathcal{T}_{js}	tensor representation of subject s in hospital j , $\mathcal{T}_{js} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r \times n_v}$
d_0	number of initial attributes for each node
\mathbf{V}^0	a node attributes identity matrix, $\mathbf{V}^0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times d_0}$
l	number of graph convolution layers used in DGN architecture
\mathbf{v}_j^l	output vector of DGN architecture with l layers in hospital j , $\mathbf{v}_j^l \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times 1}$
\mathbf{C}_j	estimated CBT \mathbf{C}_j , $\mathbf{C}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$
S	set of randomly selected training sample indices
\mathbf{C}_{js}	generated CBT for subject s of hospital c , $\mathbf{C}_{js} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$
λ_v	normalization term for brain graph connectivity weights of view v used in SNL loss function
\mathcal{W}_j^t	model weight of all layers of hospital j in round t
ts^j	the round where hospital j is trained the latest

A- Training c fraction of hospitals and sending models’ weights to the server. We propose a federated pipeline with n hospital where n/c of them are selected randomly with replacement for training in each round. We follow [5] to estimate a CBT of a given multigraph population. We denote hospitals that will be trained in round t as $TH^t = \{TH_1^t, TH_2^t, \dots, TH_k^t\}$ and those left untrained as $H^t = \{H_1^t, H_2^t, \dots, H_{n-k}^t\}$. We represent the training set of multi-view brain networks of hospital j as $T_j = \{T_{j1}^1, \dots, T_{ji}^v, \dots, T_{jn}^{n_v}\}$, where T_{ji}^v denotes the v th view of subject i in hospital j . Given a population of subjects for a hospital j , each subject s in this population is represented by a tensor $\mathcal{T}_s^j \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r \times n_v}$. Here, n_v and n_r indicate the number of brain networks and number of nodes in these brain networks, respectively. Each node denotes an anatomical brain region of interest (ROI) and the weight of an edge connecting two regions models their relationship (e.g., morphological similarity or correlation in neural activity). Aside from edge multi-view attributes defined by a tensor \mathcal{T}_s^j , DGN model¹ initializes the node attributes as identity matrix $\mathbf{V}^0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times d_0}$, where d_0 denotes the number of initial attributes for each node. We used such initialization strategy since the brain connectomes we used in this study are not annotated (i.e., nodes have no extra attributes).

The local multi-view brain connectivity dataset of each hospital $j \in TH$ is fed into a DGN model consisting of 3 graph convolutional layers with edge-conditioned convolution operation [16], each followed by ReLU activation function. Let l denote the layer index in the DGN model. Following forward propagation, the output $\mathbf{V}_j^l = [\mathbf{v}_{j1}^l, \mathbf{v}_{j2}^l, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{jn_r}^l]^T$ is obtained, denoting the output of the j th hospital and l th layer. \mathbf{V}_j^l is copied across x-axis n_r times to obtain $\mathcal{R}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r \times d_l}$. \mathcal{R}_k is also transposed to obtain \mathcal{R}_k^T . Finally, element-wise absolute difference of \mathcal{R}_k and \mathcal{R}_k^T is computed. We adopt such operation since our brain connectivity weights are derived from an absolute difference operation between brain region attributes. More details about our evaluation data are provided in the following section. The resulting tensor is summed along z-axis to estimate the final CBT $\mathbf{C}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$. The generated CBT is evaluated against a random subset of the training subjects with SNL loss function for regularization [5]. Given the generated CBT \mathbf{C}_{js} for subject s of hospital j and a random subset S of training subjects indices, SNL loss function is defined as follows [5]:

$$SNL_{js} = \sum_{v=1}^{n_v} \sum_{i \in S} \|\mathbf{C}_{js} - \mathbf{T}_{ji}^v\|_F \times \lambda_v; \quad \min_{\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_l, \mathbf{b}_l} \frac{1}{|T_j|} \sum_{s=1}^{|T_j|} SNL_{js}$$

The λ_v is defined as $\lambda_v = \frac{\max\{\mu_j\}_{j=1}^{n_v}}{\mu_v}$, where μ_v is the mean of brain graph connectivity weights of view v .

Each hospital, either trained or not, computes the Frobenius distance between its own local testing dataset and the generated CBT \mathbf{C}_k using their latest model weights. Following the backward propagation phase of the trained hospitals,

¹ <https://github.com/basiralab/DGN>

updated model weights and their corresponding loss values are sent to the server. As for the remaining hospitals, weights of the models received from server and their corresponding losses are simply passed back to the server without training.

B- Global model update strategy. In this part, we detail the federated optimization step. In this step, all N hospitals in the pipeline send their model weights to the server at the end of round t . We can denote hospital j 's loss in round t as follows:

$$f_j(\mathcal{W}_j^t) = \frac{1}{|T_j|} \sum_{i=1}^{T_j} SNL(\mathcal{T}_{ji}; \mathcal{W}_j^t)$$

Using the function above, we can express the federated loss function of all hospitals in round t as follows [14]:

$$f(\mathcal{W}^t) = \sum_{j=1}^K f_j(\mathcal{W}_j^t)$$

We, on the other hand, formulate the federated model's weights in the following way:

$$\mathcal{W}^{t+1} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathcal{W}_n^t$$

where, \mathcal{W}_n^t denotes the weights of all layers of the n th hospital in the t th round and \mathcal{W}^{t+1} is the federated weights of all layers in the following $(t + 1)$ round.

However, we note that some hospitals can be trained more than others since the selection of hospitals to train in the next round is fully stochastic. In this scenario, equally averaging all models' weights might dilute the weights of the models trained more than others (i.e., vanishing weights). To eliminate such a problem we adopt a temporally weighted aggregation strategy [17]. In this way, the more recently a hospital is selected to be trained, the stronger the contribution of its weights to the following round. Adding this trick to the model aggregation strategy is formalized by the following equation:

$$\mathcal{W}^{t+1} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\left(\frac{\text{exp}}{2}\right)^{-(t-ts^n)}}{\sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{\text{exp}}{2}\right)^{-(t-ts^n)}} \mathcal{W}_n^t$$

where t and ts^j denote the current round and the round where hospital j is trained the latest, respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

Dataset. We evaluated our Fed-CBT, federated DGN with temporary-weighted averaging (TW), and Fed-CBT w/o TW strategies against DGN model [5]

Fig. 2: Centeredness comparison between CBTs generated by DGN, Fed-CBT w/o TW and Fed-CBT. Different strategies are evaluated using the Frobenius distance between the learned CBT and testing brain networks. We kept testing sets of each fold of each dataset the same across different strategies. We also included the average Frobenius distances across all folds for each dataset. ASD: autism spectrum disorder. NC: normal control. LH: left hemisphere. RH: right hemisphere.

and against each other using normal control (NC) and autism spectrum disorder (ASD) dataset, collected from the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange ABIDE-I public dataset [18]. NC/ASD dataset consists of 186 subjects with normal control and 155 subjects with autism spectrum disorder involving both hemisphere, right and left. Cortical hemispheres are reconstructed from T1-weighted MRI using FreeSurfer [19]. Next, each one is they are parcellated into 35 ROIs using Desikan-Killiany Atlas [20]. For each cortical hemisphere, each individual in the dataset is represented by a connectivity tensor including 6 cortical

morphological brain networks as introduced in [21,22,23]: cortical surface area, minimum principle area, maximum principal curvature, mean cortical thickness, mean sulcal depth, and average curvature. The brain connectivity weight for each cortical view denotes their dissimilarity in morphology. Specifically, we first compute the average of a specific cortical attribute in a cortical region of interest. Next, we generate the connectivity weight between two regions by computing the absolute difference between their average cortical attributes (e.g., sulcal depth).

Hyperparameter tuning. We benchmarked three different strategies for comparison: DGN without federation, DGN with federation and DGN with federation using temporary-weighted strategy on 4 multiview-connectomic datasets, respectively: ASD LH, ASD RH, NC LH and NC RH. For each strategy, then, we used 3-fold cross-validation to evaluate the generalizability of our method and benchmarks against shifts in training and testing data distributions. For our DGN, we adopted the same architecture as in [5] comprising 3 edge-conditioned convolution layers, each followed by ReLU activation function. Grid search is used to set the learning rate and random sample size for training. We trained all strategies using 750 rounds with an early stop mechanism of 11 rounds. In order to simulate a real clinical scenario, we used few hospitals such as three for the federation pipeline. This means we again split the training set of each fold into 3 parts to train each method. For DGN we trained 3 different models, each with training dataset of each client in every fold and tested it with the test dataset of every fold. For Fed-CBT w/o TW we set c to 0.91 and e to 1. We averaged only hospitals trained in the current round in order to obtain the global model. For Fed-CBT, finally, we set c to 0.33 and e to 1. We averaged all hospitals’ weights based on the last time they are trained.

CBT evaluation. We evaluated our method against benchmarks in terms of CBT centeredness and representativeness. Specifically, we used the Frobenius distance between the learned CBT from the training set and all brain views in the test set, which is defined as $d_F(A, B) = \sqrt{\sum_i \sum_j |A_{ij} - B_{ij}|^2}$. We compared each hospital’s Frobenius distance across different strategies for each fold of each dataset (**Fig. 2**). We also report the average Frobenius distance across folds for each dataset and each hospital. We found out that Fed-CBT and Fed-CBT w/o TW outperform DGN across all four datasets. We also note that Fed-CBT further outperforms Fed-CBT w/o TW in ASD LH, ASD RH and NC RH datasets. **Fig. 3** displays the estimated CBTs of ASD LH dataset for each strategy: DGN, Fed-CBT w/o TW and Fed-CBT.

Limitations and future directions. One key limitation of this work is that proposed federated multigraph integration approach has only been evaluated in the case where hospitals share the same number of brain connectivity views. We will extend our work by designing a novel federated integration strategy that handles variation in the number of the brain connectivity views. The communication cost between the server and clients can also be decreased by adopting efficient strategies as proposed in [24] and [25].

Fig. 3: The learned CBTs based on different strategies. ASD RH dataset is partitioned into three folds where each fold is further partitioned into three sets, each assigned to a single hospital. Here we display the learned CBT using fold 1 by DGN, Fed-CBT w/o TW and Fed-CBT strategies, respectively.

4 Conclusion

In this work, we presented the first *federated brain multigraph integration* framework across a set of hospitals where multi-view brain connectivity datasets are locally collected. We showed that hospitals can share their knowledge and boost the representativeness of their locally learned CBTs without resorting to any clinical data sharing. In our future work, we will extend our proposed Fed-CBT to handle connectomic datasets coming in varying number of views across hospitals. We will also evaluate our framework on multi-modal brain connectivity

datasets derived from different modalities such as resting state functional and diffusion MRIs.

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